

13th ANNUAL REPORT

Year Ended June 30, 1969

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
One Dupont Circle, Washington, D.C. 20036

Library: Goddard Space Flight Center

*Or dreams he sees, while overhead the Moon
Sits as arbitress and nearer to the Earth
Wheels her pale course . . .*

— Milton, *Paradise Lost*, I.

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During the fiscal year 1968-69 the Council on Library Resources was located at 1028 Connecticut Ave., N.W., Washington, D. C.

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
JULY 1, 1968 — JUNE 30, 1969

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[°] Professor Morse was succeeded by Dr. Dix November 23, 1968.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

In 1960 and again in 1967 the Ford Foundation approved new grants totalling thirteen million dollars to enable the Council to carry forward its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems.

The Council conducts much of its work through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

INTRODUCTION

The Year 1968-1969

It is evident, as one reviews the developments of the past fiscal year, that public attitudes toward libraries and librarianship are changing significantly. Less and less are libraries looked upon as of secondary importance to society, with an incidental educational and recreational value; they are more and more regarded as essential elements of modern life, with a potential for service far beyond anything previously envisaged.

Libraries are viewed and measured today not only in relation to their importance to education and cultural pursuits, but also in relation to research, industrial technology and commerce, and to their potential role in meeting some of the age's pressing social needs. We see this reflected in the demand for quick access — "over-the-counter service" it has been called — to materials without limit. We see it reflected in the statements of politicians and educators. We see it reflected in government attitudes. Government assistance to education is not new in this country, but the Federal Government's concern about libraries other than its own — as exemplified, say, in library aid programs — is a rather recent development. Ten or fifteen years ago the idea of a National Advisory Commission, appointed by the President to consider "the role and adequacy of our libraries," would have seemed wishful thinking, improbable of realization. But in 1966 such a temporary Commission *was* created, and now a bill to establish a permanent commission has passed the Senate and a similar bill is in the House of Representatives.

The rising academic enrollments, the increasing volume of publications, the mounting demands of science and technology for "hard" information — much of it in data centers, periodicals, or report literature — are propelling libraries toward national systems and networks. This is happening not because of any magnetic attraction toward centralization for its own sake, but because planned cooperation and standardization of practices offer the principal hope for meeting growing requirements.

The urgent demands upon library funds make it essential to seek new tools and modes of operation. But at present automated systems and other technological developments are expensive to devise and to operate. Traditional methods and procedures must be improved because in large part they must continue to serve as the basis for current library service and for automation when it comes. This country and others face a dilemma. Unless large sums

of money are invested in library experimentation and development in the near future, a tremendous loss in the efficiency and satisfaction of society will result. Libraries may approach bankruptcy if they invest as they should; they will be smothered with paper or starved in isolation if they do not.

The Council will of course continue its interest in technology and systems as they relate to intralibrary operation; however it is increasingly concerned with networks of service on the national and subnational level. Greater thought must be given also to international library relations if we hope to achieve maximum efficiency in resources and services.

It is true that the problems faced by libraries are varied and complex and that long-range programs will perhaps offer the only solutions. However, a significant beginning has been made, with a multiplying effect that will grow and spread as Government, industry, the public, academic institutions, and the libraries themselves become more deeply aware of the vital contribution the library can make to the quality of life in this age of moon flights.

FRED C. COLE
President

Projects Commenced or Completed 1968-1969

I. ARCHIVES

Status of the National Archives The National Archives of the United States functioned as an independent agency from its establishment in 1934 until 1949 when it was integrated into the newly established General Services Administration as the National Archives and Records Service. The General Services Administration is in effect the Federal Government's housekeeper — charged with management of such matters as construction and operation of buildings, procurement and distribution of supplies, disposal of surplus property, and stockpiling of strategic and critical materials. Because of widespread concern about the ability of the National Archives and Records Service to function effectively within the framework of such an agency, a joint committee representing the American Historical Association, the Organization of American Historians, and the Society of American Archivists was established in December 1966 to study the situation. Dr. Julian P. Boyd, editor of the *Papers of Thomas Jefferson* and former president of the American Historical Association, served as chairman, and the Council made a small grant to assist the committee's work.¹ The study has been completed and a report published.² This is a revision of a preliminary report and includes Dr. Boyd's dissenting statement upholding the views originally expressed. The project resulted also in a book-length account of the National Archives, its history and current situation, by the North Carolina archivist and historian, Dr. H. G. Jones, who served as secretary of the committee.³ The author is of the opinion that it is in the best interests of the nation that Archives be separated from the General Services Administration and reestablished as an independent authority.

¹ XI: 10-11; XII: 11. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports: for example to the 11th Annual Report, pages 10-11.

² *Report of the Joint Committee on the Status of the National Archives to the American Historical Association, Organization of American Historians, Society of American Archivists, July 1968.* [Washington, American Historical Association, 1969.] 20 p.

³ H. G. Jones. *The Records of a Nation, Their Management, Preservation, and Use.* With an Introduction by Wayne C. Grover. New York, Atheneum, 1969. xviii, 309 p. III.

Academic A problem confronting university archivists is the
Scientific proper management of the records of scientific re-
Research search conducted at their institutions. Although the
volume of such records increases very rapidly, there
has been little published on the subject. A Council grant to the
University of Illinois enabled Maynard J. Brichford, University
Archivist, to prepare a study which might lead to the develop-
ment of a body of good practice to assure the identification and
preservation of valuable portions of the records and disposal of
the remainder.⁴ The study has been completed and a report in
the nature of a manual published.⁵ The policies and procedures
outlined in it are sufficiently general to be of interest to all who
are concerned with the archival aspects of scientific and tech-
nological documentation.

II. AUTOMATION

Readers of these reports are aware that the Council has from
its establishment entertained high hopes for the ultimately bene-
ficial effects of automation on library work, but that it has never-
theless been studious to avoid the costly mistakes which have too
often attended attempts to automate library procedures. The
Council believes that, as a result, it has been able to contribute
significantly to steady, planned, progress in this field at relatively
low expense. However, because of the amount and complexity of
activity in this area, a preliminary word may be useful as to the
relationship and significance of the several projects which the
Council is currently supporting.

The Council early concluded that successful automation of
libraries was completely dependent upon the availability of biblio-
graphic information in a standardized machine-readable form,
preferably from a central source. *Project MARC* is the operating
expression of that conclusion; it is actually providing libraries
with a machine-readable version of the Library of Congress' current
output of printed catalog cards of English language titles. How-
ever, the current record by itself is insufficient for library
needs; the retrospective record is required to complement it, and
to supply this is the objective of *Project RECON*. But the Library

⁴ X: 59.

⁵ Maynard J. Brichford. *Scientific and Technological Documentation, Archival Evaluation and Processing of University Records Relating to Science and Technology*. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, 1969. 35 p. Processed. 28 cms.

of Congress is not the only Federal agency supplying bibliographic information to libraries, and it is important that in these matters all *Three National Libraries* employ the same standards so as to contribute maximally to national compatibility of practice. At the same time, while concerned with the supply, the Council has not neglected potential consumers of this information. In the *NELINET project* it is assisting six university libraries to develop procedures for utilizing the MARC information; in *Project LISTS* it is similarly assisting pilot application to various library operations of on-line computer services from a central facility; and in the abortive *International Business Machine Corporation project* it had hoped to collaborate with one of the major suppliers in this field in a demonstration of the application of its latest achievements to library work. In the *Archive of Folk Song* and the *Classification Scheme for Slides projects* it had, by contrast, supported projects in which computers play comparatively simple but eminently practical roles. Lastly, in *Project INTREX* it is assisting extremely sophisticated experimentation toward the development of the university library of the future.

MARC: Project to System The preceding section has taken note of the Council's early recognition that the general application of computer technology to library work would be possible only if machine-readable bibliographic data could be distributed in adequate form. This realization developed over a period of years into a sequence of grants and contracts leading to Project MARC (MACHINE Readable Cataloging),⁶ two reports concerning which have appeared during the Council's fiscal year.⁷ Using a refinement of the earlier format, Project MARC has become the MARC Distribution Service.

In March of 1969 the Card Division of the Library of Congress, drawing on a revolving fund provided by a grant from the Council, began the regular sale of magnetic tapes containing cataloging information in a standard format. Now more than 50 subscribers to the MARC Distribution Service are receiving weekly tapes of about 1,000 catalog records each. These include all English language monographs currently being acquired by the Library.

⁶ X: 29-30, 41-42; XI: 11-12; XII: 13-14.

⁷ *The MARC Pilot Experience, An Informal Summary*. Washington, Library of Congress, Information Systems Office. June 1968. 15 l. 26½ cms. *The MARC Pilot Project. Final Report on a Project Sponsored by the Council on Library Resources, Inc.* Prepared by Henriette D. Avram. Washington, Library of Congress, 1968 [1969]. [iii,] 183 p. 20 cms.

The final report of the MARC Pilot Project may have understated the case in observing, "The single most significant result of MARC has been the impetus to set standards. There is no doubt that eventually standards would have been designed for machine-readable bibliographic records, character sets, and codes for such elements as place and language. MARC accelerated standardization and still more important, the standards are being set and agreed to by a large segment of the library community." The National Task Force on Automation and Other Cooperative Services — representing the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and the National Agricultural Library — is one of several groups to adopt the new MARC format. Overseas it is the basis of the United Kingdom MARC Pilot Project sponsored by the British National Bibliography.

A most important activity arising from the development of MARC is the series of MARC Seminars sponsored by the Library of Congress and the Information Science and Automation Division of the American Library Association. LC Information Systems Office staff members as well as systems specialists from other libraries have presented the Seminars at which approximately 1,000 librarians have received detailed two-day explanations of the meaning of the MARC program and the structure of the standardized bibliographic format on which it is based.

REtrospective The MARC program has been concerned with
CONversion current cataloging only; it has not attempted to cover what has been done in the past. There is, however, widespread interest in and indeed an urgent need for converting the earlier cataloging records to machine-readable form in order to provide a comprehensive store of bibliographic information. Individual libraries with computer facilities have begun converting their own records, but with uncoordinated conversion there is the likelihood that the resulting product will not be standard, nationally or internationally. Because of the heavy and increasing amount of overlap among the collections of American research libraries, unilateral conversions would also involve duplication of effort costing millions and requiring an enormous amount of manpower. Since the Library of Congress, with its nationally important collection, has been trying to come to grips with the problem of converting its retrospective catalog, the Council made a grant to that institution for a study of the

FLOW CHART showing steps involved in preparing and disseminating retrospective bibliographic records in machine-readable form at the Library of Congress for a projected national service to libraries. (From Conversion of Retrospective Catalog Records to Machine Readable-Form, Library of Congress, 1969.)

feasibility of a major assault on this problem. The study⁸ was carried out by a working task force of librarians and computer systems analysts representing various types of libraries, under the guidance of an advisory committee.

The principal outcome of the investigation was the general conclusion that large-scale centralized conversion should indeed be attempted under the direction of the Library of Congress, with its Official Catalog as the data base. Other conclusions stated in the report issued by the task force included:

- The MARC Distribution Service should be expanded to cover all languages and all forms of material as rapidly as resources and technology allow. There should be no conversion of any category of retrospective records until that category is being currently converted.
- Conversion of some portion of retrospective records to machine-readable form should be an early goal of library automation efforts.
- Standards for conversion should be the same as those for current records.
- The highest priority should be given to records most likely to be useful to the largest number of libraries.

Among the specific recommendations were:

- The initial conversion should be limited to English language monograph records issued from 1960 to date. Second priority should be given to Romance and German language monograph records issued from 1960.
- Every effort should be made to convert priority one and two records within four years. Conversion should start with the most recent year and proceed backward in reverse chronological order.
- There should be a study of the problems of creating a complete national bibliographic data store, including determination of the best means of obtaining standardized records for bibliographic items not in the Library of Congress record set.

In pursuit of the goals detailed in these conclusions and recommendations, the Council has made a grant to supplement funds appropriated by the Library of Congress for a pilot project. This seeks to establish definitive methods for conversion and to determine costs. In addition, it will convert to MARC format the

⁸ *Conversion of Retrospective Catalog Records to Machine-Readable Form, A Study of the Feasibility of a National Bibliographic Service*. Prepared by the RECON Working Task Force: Henriette D. Avram, Chairman, . . . Washington, Library of Congress, 1969. x, 230 p. 26 cms. Processed.

Library's catalog records for 1968 English language monographs as well as those 1969 English language monographs not previously covered by the current MARC program.

The progress of scholarship, particularly in the humanities and social sciences, is seriously hampered by the inability of libraries to produce their materials in the forms needed by scholars for their studies. RECON's potential value to scholarship is enormous – far exceeding its cost, great though that will probably be.

The Three National Libraries The creation of a joint Task Force on Automation and Other Cooperative Services by the National Library of Medicine, National Agricultural Library, and the Library of Congress in the spring of 1967 was a major step in the development of library service. The goals of this cooperative effort are the development of a national data bank of machine-readable cataloging information, of a similar bank of information on the location of the thousands of serial titles in American research libraries, and the achievement of the maximum possible degree of compatibility in the practices of the three libraries. As mentioned in the Council's preceding annual report, when the National Library of Medicine found that as a result of a limitation on personnel it was unable to participate adequately in the activities of the Task Force, the Council employed an experienced systems specialist and assigned him to Task Force duties at the Library of Medicine. This year the Council has employed a second specialist to reinforce the work.

Task Force groups are involved in a number of investigations relating to compatibility and problems of design. The program is intricate, but progress is good. As the Deputy Librarian of Congress, John G. Lorenz, said in an address at a recent international meeting,⁹ the Task Force's accomplishments "in a relatively brief period of time have been rather remarkable, particularly when it is recognized that many involve problem areas in which sceptics expressed doubt that any compatibility could be achieved – at least in our lifetime."

New England Board of Higher Education The Council has continued its interest in the development of the New England Library Information Network (NELINET), making this year its fifth grant to the New England Board of Higher Education for the purpose.¹⁰ NELINET, regional

⁹ First Japan - U.S. Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education: Tokyo, May 15-19, 1969.

¹⁰ XI: 12-14; XII: 12.

in concept, is a pioneering effort to establish a computer-aided technical processing center utilizing large machine-form data bases. It has progressed from the original systems analysis of the libraries of the New England state universities to a pilot operation in which six libraries are receiving on an experimental basis tailored catalog products – conventional catalog cards with call numbers and overprinted headings, and book labels. Priority has been given to cataloging services. When these are fully developed NELINET plans to move on to other services – acquisitions (searching, order control, processing, acquisitions accounting); accession list, union list, and book form catalog production; circulation and interlibrary loan control; library management information; and remote data base interrogation. NELINET's use of the MARC format,¹¹ adapted to local system and individual library needs, assures national network compatibility when the time comes.

Project INTREX (*Information Transfer Experiments*) is a continuing investigation at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology of the bases on which an engineering and scientific library of the future may be modeled. The Council, which made its first contributions toward the support of INTREX in January 1967, has continued its interest in the project.¹²

By and large, the information contained in libraries is in the form of printed materials or in microform copies. In the future some information will be stored in digital and otherwise encoded forms, but it is likely that for many years the bulk of the information contained in libraries will continue to be in traditional format. Any satisfactory information network should provide quick access to this material. The user should have the opportunity to obtain a copy to keep, if he so desires. The system should be capable also of providing rapid service, even to several readers requesting the same material at the same time.

The implementation of these functions at Project INTREX takes the form of a Text-Access system which utilizes television technology to transmit images from a centrally located automated microform bank to remote user terminals incorporating cathode

¹¹ NELINET – New England Library Information Network. *Demonstration of Cataloging Support Services and MARC II Conversion*. Prepared by Lawrence F. Buckland, Ann T. Curran, William R. Nugent. Submitted to the New England Board of Higher Education. Final Report Contract No. CLR-425. January 2, 1969. Inforonics Inc., Cambridge, Massachusetts. [39 1.] Processed. 28 cms.

¹² XI: 14-15; XII: 13.

ray tube displays, mechanisms for rapidly reproducing the microforms, and equipment for converting microforms to full-sized paper copies.

The Council's original assistance to Project INTREX was directed toward the Text-Access system, now in experimental operation at M.I.T., but support has been broadened to include work on an Augmented Catalog—a remote-access computer-based catalog, augmented with respect to a conventional catalog in the broad inclusiveness of publications made available, the extensive number of identified subjects and references in each article, and the provisions for users easily to conduct a productive dialogue with the machine in searching and retrieving the desired information. Like the Text-Access system, work on the Augmented Catalog has progressed to the point where it is to be a feature of the experimental model engineering library M.I.T. plans to have in operation in late 1969 or early 1970.

LISTS The Council this year contracted with the System Development Corporation for the testing and appraisal of a Library Information System Time-Sharing System (LISTS) that the Corporation has been developing since 1967. The basic concept is to permit libraries to share the resources of a computer without the need for interlibrary standardization of procedures or data formats, or other restrictions on the autonomy of each library.

Seven Southern California libraries, varying in purpose and in size from 56,000 to 1,200,000 volumes and including a special library with 18,000 volumes and 86,000 technical documents, agreed to participate in the testing of LISTS in their day-to-day work. They are: San Marino Public, Beverly Hills Public, Pierce and Fullerton junior colleges, University of California at Riverside, University of Southern California, and the special library of the System Development Corporation. Teletype terminals installed in the libraries will link them with the Corporation's time-shared computer in Santa Monica. Library functions to be covered in the investigation include: acquisitions, accounting, book and card catalog production, the serials record system, production of bibliographies, and circulation control. MARC tapes will be used where appropriate.

The project seeks answers to two basic questions:

- Is automation clearly an improvement over manual operation?
- Is the cost of automation tolerable, especially to small and medium-sized libraries, even when the computer support is time-shared?

It may be that the costs are too great; it may be that automated and manual costs are about the same; or, possibly, that computer support — even at a higher cost — is desirable because it can free highly trained personnel from clerical tasks to work on more professional ones.

Indexing the Archive of Folk Song With the help of a Council grant,¹³ the Music Division of the Library of Congress has found that it is feasible to automate the cataloging of the Division's Archive of Folk Song. LC's Information Systems Office cooperated in the study, which dealt with the approximately 40,000 non-foreign sound recordings in the collection. The investigation indicated that there is little difference in cost between different levels of cataloging and that therefore the "full treatment" would be advisable. Automated cataloging of the collection has been deferred, however, until such time as adequate funds become available.

Classification Scheme for Slides With the aid of a grant from the Council,¹⁴ the library of the University of California, Santa Cruz, has created a classification scheme for a collection of slides designed to support an interdisciplinary approach to teaching. The new system is divided into three basic divisions — history, art, and science. A preliminary checking edition of the classification system for history and art has been prepared,¹⁵ and the Council has made a new grant to assist development of the science division. When this is finished, it is expected that the complete system will be published.

Library Management System A unique opportunity to develop a model library situation presented itself when the International Business Machine Corporation's Advanced Systems Development Laboratory in Los Gatos, California, proposed that the Council provide partial financial support for the continued development of a computer-based system for carrying out the intellectual and "housekeeping" functions of sizeable research libraries.

¹³ XI: 17.

¹⁴ XII: 15-16.

¹⁵ Wendell W. Simons and Luraine C. Tansey. *A Universal Slide Collection With Automatic Indexing*. Preliminary Edition. University of California, Santa Cruz, The University Library, January 1969. iii, 183 1. 27½ cms. Processed.

The fact that the proposal was initiated by one of the largest producers of hardware and software (that is, both physical equipment and associated programs) in the field added considerably to its interest, for it might then be possible to direct industry's efficiency and know-how into channels benefiting libraries. Since libraries represent a relatively small market commercially, they have received only peripheral attention from industry; this cooperative effort with IBM might be a means of altering the situation. Further, since so many colleges and universities either have or are acquiring the Series 360 computer on which the project was based, the manufacturer was more than ordinarily motivated to provide good documentation.

As part of the proposal the Council was asked to recruit an appropriate library to serve as test bed and demonstration site for the system. An agreement was reached for a three-phase program to culminate in operation of the full system in the selected library. However, after further investigation, IBM discovered they had seriously underestimated not only the complexity of the problem but the cost of the equipment required — a cost which would place the system far beyond the capability of most institutions. The Corporation therefore requested that the agreement be nullified.

Library Planning at Santa Cruz A valuable by-product of the foregoing was a three-month systems study (Phase I of the proposed project) of the library at the University of California at Santa Cruz, the institution selected by the Council for the demonstration site. Long-range plans at Santa Cruz are for expansion from four to an eventual 25 or more colleges served by centralized university library facilities. The Council-supported study has been completed, and provided guidance for applying computer techniques to appropriate operations at that institution.

III. BIBLIOGRAPHIES

Victorian Periodicals 1824-1900 Victorian periodical literature is an important resource for scholars. But the lack of indexes and the fact that much of the authorship is veiled in anonymity and pseudonymity have prevented its full use. For more than a decade Professor Walter E. Houghton, of Wellesley College, and his collaborators have been working on the *Wellesley Index to Victorian Periodicals 1824-1900*; the first

volume of this work was published in 1966 and immediately received acclaim. A surprising but nonetheless gratifying feature was that in about 85 percent of the instances of concealed authorship the writers were identified. Work has continued on the *Wellesley Index*, and this year the Council has made a small matching grant to the National Endowment for the Humanities to support it.

Urdu Mss in the United Kingdom The United Kingdom contains considerable manuscript material relating to the area which was once British India. The Council has made a grant to the School of Librarianship and Archives, University College, London, for a Pakistani student, Syed Mazher Ali Zaidi, to search out and prepare a catalog of Urdu language manuscripts, of which there are believed to be about 1,000 in the United Kingdom.

Library Work for Children Two previous annual reports¹⁶ have made reference to the preparation of a one-volume compilation of all sources of printed information pertaining to the history of children's literature and its current state of development. The work, by Anne Pellowski, Director-Librarian of the Information Center on Children's Cultures of the United States Committee for UNICEF, was published this fiscal year.¹⁷

IV. BOOK SELECTION & PROCUREMENT

Public Law 480 A section of the Public Law 480 Program provides for the acquisition of foreign books, periodicals, and other materials and their deposit in libraries and research centers within the United States. They are paid for with local currencies derived from the sale of U.S. agricultural surpluses abroad. The countries involved are Ceylon, India, Indonesia, Israel, Nepal, Pakistan, the United Arab Republic, and Yugoslavia. Since the first shipments were made in January 1962, a total of 9,374,211 pieces has been received as of June 30, 1968. Forty-one libraries, including the Library of Congress, receive complete sets of the materials from one or more of the participating countries; approximately 300 libraries receive English-language materials on a selective basis.

¹⁶ X: 45; XI: 18.

¹⁷ Anne Pellowski. *The World of Children's Literature*. New York and London, R. R. Bowker Company, 1968. x, 538 p. 27½ cms.

Public Law 480 has figured in previous annual reports of the Council.¹⁸ The Eleventh Annual Report listed a grant to the American Council of Learned Societies to enable Dr. Mortimer Graves, who as acting director of ACLS played a part in the law's enactment, to make a study of the usefulness of the program. This year the Council made a grant to Columbia University, under which Tahany El-Arian, a candidate for the doctoral degree in the School of Library Service, will make a study that complements the earlier one. Whereas Dr. Graves' is concerned with the user, hers deals with recipient libraries and such matters as delays in cataloging P.L. 480 materials, possible space problems, effect of the Program on acquisition policies, and the like. It is anticipated that when the two reports are completed they will provide a basis for possible recommendations for improvement in the Program.

V. CATALOGING

International Cataloging The Council's long-standing interest in promoting cooperation and standardization in cataloging, on both the national and international level, has been related in previous annual reports.¹⁹ That interest was further demonstrated this year with two grants to the International Federation of Library Associations' Committee on Uniform Cataloguing Rules for a working meeting of specialists. The purpose of the August 1969 sessions in Copenhagen was to review developments since the 1961 International Conference on Cataloguing Principles and to consider the prospects for further advances through standardization and mechanization. About forty experts were invited to participate; the subjects for discussion included an international standard identifying number for each book, problems arising from shared cataloging, and the implications of the British and American MARC projects.

VI. LIBRARY ADMINISTRATION

Growing enrollments, expanding academic programs, and the increasing volume of publications have caused academic libraries to expand their facilities, services, and staff far beyond the expectations and plans of only a few years ago. The forecasts are for further expansion in the decade ahead.

¹⁸ IV: 16; V: 31; XI: 20-21.

¹⁹ For example, XI: 21-24.

Some indication of where matters stand is to be found in statistics compiled by the Association of Research Libraries from information supplied by its 71 member libraries in the academic year 1967-68. The total operating expenditures of the 71 libraries was \$177,971,806, with the individual amounts ranging from Georgetown's \$646,000 to Harvard's \$7,379,198. The median for 1967-68 was \$2,040,689, compared to \$1,889,650 for 1966-67.

Management Practices Cost/benefit program planning and similar management techniques, long used by government and industry, are urgently needed by academic libraries in order to keep pace with the mounting demands made upon them. Use of this kind of professional management approach would also place the libraries in a position to justify their needs to the administrators of the parent institutions.

With a grant from the Council the Association of Research Libraries — now with 85 members — was enabled to contract with Booz, Allen & Hamilton for a preliminary study of management practices in university libraries. The study will seek to identify major needs and problems and to recommend priorities for action, indicate possible approaches to improving management, and to suggest subjects and plans for further study. This exploratory work could lead to a major program for examining administration in academic and, by extension, other kinds of libraries.

Time and Cost Analysis The Council contracted this spring with the Information General Corporation of Palo Alto for a pilot research study of time and cost analysis in two areas of library operation. At present little objective and transferable time and cost data relating to libraries is available to describe the effort required to perform certain repeatable tasks such as the keyboarding of information for input to computer files. The goal is a collection of normalized standard times and costs for repeated library operations, written and documented in a form that will permit their utilization and extrapolation in a wide variety of situations.

A Survey of Public Library Systems The standards for public libraries adopted by the American Library Association in 1956 included a basic recommendation that libraries within natural areas band together to form library systems and thereby collectively gain in resources and

staff. A decade later the Inter-library Cooperation Committee of the ALA's member Public Library Association recognized the critical need to take stock of system development. The Council provided funds for the purpose,²⁰ and a report of the study has been published.²¹

The study provides information on such aspects of multijurisdictional library systems as their legal and administrative structure, sources of financial support, collections, personnel, and services to the public. It concludes with a series of suggestions and recommendations to system directors and trustees, to state officials, and to state and national library leaders.

Pilferage The greatly accelerating incidence of book thefts from libraries in recent years has led to a search for adequate preventive measures. The Free Library of Philadelphia has during the past decade experienced annual losses from theft averaging 1.75 percent in the branch collections and reaching levels as high as 3.18 percent. After several attempts to find effective countermeasures, the Free Library in May 1967 installed at one of its branches on an experimental basis an electronic detection system called CHECKPOINT, newly developed by the Logistics Industries Corporation. The initial results were sufficiently promising for the Council to make a grant to the Free Library in December 1967 for installation of the system at three other branch libraries for further testing and tailoring the system for library use.²²

CHECKPOINT, one of several theft-detection systems now on the market, calls for pasting detector pieces — electronic laminates of metal alloys, chemicals, adhesives, and papers, with the appearance of a heavy bond paper — to the inside of books. Electronic sensing screens are installed on either side of the exit path for patrons. When a reader attempts to pass through CHECKPOINT without charging his book out, a muted alarm sounds, warning lights flash, and the exit door or turnstile locks, making it possible for the reader to be questioned.

The Free Library has completed its investigation of the system with results it considers satisfactory. It found the system

²⁰ X: 59-60; XI: 27.

²¹ *Public Library Systems in the United States, A Survey of Multijurisdictional Systems*. By Nelson Associates for the Public Library Association, American Library Association. Chicago, American Library Association, 1969. xvi, 368 p.

²² X: 19-20.

characterized by simplicity, ease of installation, and economy. Book losses were reduced to a very small fraction of their previous level and, according to the Library, "The collection is in a better, more current and more accurately recorded condition than it has ever been. Finally, we are providing much improved service to the library users." A report of the Philadelphia experience is expected to be published in a professional journal.

Cases in Library Management Courses in principles of management are taught in only a limited number of library schools, and not a great deal exists in the way of teaching materials. To help meet this need the Council in 1966 made a grant to the Indiana University Foundation to enable Dr. Mildred Hawksworth Lowell, Associate Professor of Library Science, to work on a compilation of cases in library management.²³ Three volumes have been published under the general title of *The Management of Libraries and Information Centers*.²⁴ This work has been favorably reviewed in professional journals, and an additional volume is in preparation.

Measuring Research Libraries In the previous annual report it was noted that a grant had been made to two Purdue University men for design of a study which would seek to identify those characteristics of academic library collections which contribute to successful research and graduate work.²⁵ John H. Moriarty, Director of University Libraries and Audio-Visual Center, and Warren F. Seibert, Head of the Instructional Media Research Unit, have completed their project and have submitted a report.²⁶

VII. PHOTOGRAPHIC APPLICATIONS

Over the years the Council has consistently supported the view that microforms are a primary means by which libraries might

²³ XI: 26-27.

²⁴ Mildred Hawksworth Lowell. *The Management of Libraries and Information Centers*. Volume I. *The Case Method in Teaching Library Management*. 168 p.; Volume II. *The Process of Managing: Syllabus and Cases*, 359 p.; Volume III. *Personnel Management: Syllabus and Cases*, 211 p. Metuchen, N.J., The Scarecrow Press, Inc., 1968.

²⁵ XII: 20.

²⁶ John H. Moriarty and Warren F. Seibert. *A Suggested Methodology for Relating Research Collection Criteria to Disciplines and to Educational Program Quality. A Planning Study to Council on Library Resources, Inc., Washington, D. C. Lafayette, Indiana, December, 1968.* [i.] 19 1. 28 cms. Processed.

counter space and cost problems. Toward this end the Council has in the past financed numerous projects with a variety of investigators and developers, but because of the extremely involved nature of the application of the micro-media to the library environment, the hoped-for results have been slow in coming. However, it has been particularly evident in the year 1968-69 that the seed planted in the last decade or so has taken firm root and that expenditures by the Council in this area have resulted in a sharpening of interest on the part of commercial organizations. Several of the nation's largest manufacturing and marketing organizations have in progress large-scale library microform projects. Because of this increase in commercial activity the Council in this report year has limited its financial assistance in the area to a grant to the American Library Association for a Library Technology Program-sponsored evaluation of microform readers for libraries which are available on the American market. The Council, however, retains its interest in the subject and is represented on a number of advisory panels established by others to assist in evaluating their proposed and active microform programs.

A Bibliographer's Camera The Council also made a small appropriation supplementing an earlier one,²⁷ to the R. A. Morgan Company (now Morgan Infotek) for an additional refinement of its prototype of a bibliographer's camera. The camera is intended for use in copying catalog or other bibliographic entries from books to be reproduced on paper or card stock in a scaled-down office-copying processor. The camera will be tested at the Stanford University Library.

VIII. PHYSICAL ACCESS TO LIBRARY MATERIALS

Quality Control of Input In view of the continuously growing volume and complexity of scientific publication, the subject of selection — whether for publication, indexing and abstracting, or reference — daily acquires greater importance. Data banks and computer-serviced information systems incorporate large quantities of information from a variety of sources. Retrieval by computer may produce an information output with little or no distinction of quality. Standards need to be set for labeling input so that, on retrieval, high quality

²⁷ XI: 28.

information can be distinguished from low. The Council has made a grant this year to the Federation of American Societies for Experimental Biology for development of criteria for quality control of input in science information systems. While selection criteria and experience in quality identification in the biological sciences will be used for the most part in the study, it is expected that the recommendations developed will be useful to librarians, indexers, and information specialists in other fields.

IX. PLANNING

Economic Improvement The responsibilities implicit in the growth of higher education and the technical developments becoming more and more available to libraries underscore the urgent need to attract young people of exceptional ability to the library profession. Unfortunately, the economic rewards and benefits offered librarians are on the whole not competitive with those of comparable professions. For example, only five percent of the librarians employed in member institutions of the Association of Research Libraries earn \$15,000 or more a year. It is evident that higher salaries are limited largely to those engaged in administrative work. This is not true elsewhere in the university salary structure: full professors are numerous in faculties, as are associate and assistant professors. For an attractive picture of librarianship as a career to be presented to potential recruits, it is desirable that higher salaries based on merit be paid to librarians with, say, bibliographic, reference, or similar specialized responsibilities. This is not likely to occur without solid information on which recommendations can be based.

For approximately a year Donald F. Cameron, formerly director of the Rutgers University Library, has been engaged as a part-time consultant to the Council on a preliminary study of the possibility of developing a regular data-gathering and evaluating system for assessing the salaries of academic librarians.

Assuming that a valid system for gathering statistics is devised and that the resulting information supports the conviction that the library profession is badly placed in the competition for recruiting able personnel, it is believed that ensuing publicity may lead to improvement of the situation. The statistics thus gathered will also be most useful in other areas of the profession.

Resources of Canadian University Libraries Some years ago a Library Survey Committee of the National Conference of Canadian Universities and Colleges urged that a national plan for coordinated institutional specialization be developed as a method of correcting limitations in the collections available for research in the humanities and social sciences, and that as a first step an independent objective survey be made of existing resources and needs. The Council made it possible for an experienced Harvard librarian, Edwin E. Williams, to conduct the survey, and a report was published in 1962.²⁸ The success of this limited project encouraged the Association of Universities and Colleges of Canada (successor to the National Conference) and the Canadian Association of College and University Libraries to embark on a broader national study, headed by Robert B. Downs, Dean of Library Administration, University of Illinois, and supported by the Canada Council and the Council on Library Resources.²⁹ The report, published in English and French editions,³⁰ contains numerous recommendations relating to collections, operating techniques, service, administration, and finance. A "Libraries for Tomorrow" conference in Montreal in April 1968 described the report as the "cornerstone" on which Canadian research libraries should build.

A National Foreign Newspaper Microfilm Project The Association of Research Libraries' Foreign Newspaper Microfilm Project as now constituted was established in 1956. The project assures research libraries and their users that at least one microfilm file of approximately 200 leading newspapers published throughout the world will be permanently available. While the foreign newspapers now being microfilmed are those most in demand, there are libraries whose users need greater coverage. The Council has made a grant for a study to determine what additional coverage may be needed, the specific newspapers which should be included in an initial list for filming, and the institutions willing to participate in the program. The study is expected to result also in recommendations covering the organizational and administrative requirements for establishing and coordinating such a program on a continuing basis.

²⁸ VI: 39; VII: 19-20.

²⁹ XI: 31-32.

³⁰ Robert B. Downs. *Resources of Canadian Academic and Research Libraries*. Ottawa, Association of Universities and Colleges of Canada, 1967. xi, 301 p. *Ressources des bibliothèques d'Université et de recherche au Canada*, Traduit de l'anglais par J.-M. Arbic, . . .

A State Research Depository Library The Council this year made a grant to the North Carolina State Board of Higher Education for a study of the feasibility of a central depository library to serve the entire state. Participating with the State Board of Higher Education in the proposal were the North Carolina State Library, the North Carolina Library Association, and the North Carolina Board of Education. The depository, as conceived, would be a cooperative state-supported facility to which participating academic libraries of both public and private institutions, public libraries, and the special libraries of private industry and government could send little-used materials. The group is giving consideration in the initial planning to participation in future cooperative programs.

The Federal Library Committee The Federal Library Committee – which works for the improvement of communication, coordination, and planning among the approximately 2,500 diverse libraries operated by the United States Government – has been mentioned in previous annual reports.³¹ The Committee is served by a small secretariat located in the Library of Congress and headed by Librarian of Congress L. Quincy Mumford as chairman and Paul Howard as executive secretary. It has a number of task forces at work on such subjects and projects as: an analysis of the collections of selected Federal libraries with extensive or unique subject collections of research materials; automation; procurement policies and practices. Among the publications resulting in the past year from the Committee's work is a procurement manual and a *Guide to Laws and Regulations on Federal Libraries*.³² Though a compilation of laws and regulations pertaining to Government libraries had

³¹ III: 40-1; VIII: 44-5; IX: 45-6; X: 58-9; XI: 31.

³² Leslie K. Falk. *Procurement of Library Materials in the Federal Government. An Orientation Aid Prepared for the Federal Library Committee*. Washington, D. C. The Federal Library Committee, 1968. [vi,] 42 p. 26 cms.

William Strauss, Armins Ruis, Ivan Sipkov. *Guide to Laws and Regulations on Federal Libraries, A Compilation and Analysis*. [New York R. R. Bowker Company, 1968.] [xii,] 862 p. 28 cms.

Some other publications, issued by the Federal Library Committee: Paul Howard, *The Federal Library Committee, Three Years of Progress, 1965-1968*, 13 p. 26½ cms.; *Roster of Federal Libraries, Alphabetically by State and City*, 1967, 35 p. 26½ cms.; *Survey of Special Libraries Serving the Federal Government* [U. S. Department of Health, Education and Welfare, Office of Education, 1968] viii, 108 p. 26 cms.; *Federal Libraries Interlibrary Loan Code*, 1968. i, 6 p. 26½ cms.

been talked about for many years, the present work is the first to be completed. It is a particularly useful reference tool inasmuch as the laws and regulations included are scattered throughout the United States Code, the Code of Federal Regulations, and regulations issued by the various Federal agencies.

Federal Libraries & Extra-Library Information Systems The Federal Library Committee is now firmly established and independent of Council support. This past year, however, the Council made a grant for a project relating to the Committee's effort to obtain the basic information upon which a comprehensive Federal library program can be built. The grant was to the Office, Chief of Engineers, United States Army, for an investigation of the origins and reasons for the establishment of extra-library information storage, analysis and retrieval systems; their place within the structure of representative Federal agencies selected for study; their relationship to technical libraries within their agencies; and for identification of common and unique functions of the libraries and the extra-library systems. The investigation is being carried out under contract by the National Academy of Public Administration with assistance from the Federal Library Committee's Task Force on the Role of Libraries in Information Systems.

Some Meetings A first Japan-U.S. Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education was held in Tokyo in May 1969, with assistance from the Ford Foundation and the Council on Library Resources. Twenty-three U.S. representatives were among the nearly 400 participants at the Conference, which was sponsored by the American Library Association and Japan's leading academic library organizations. The committees established at the Conference—to serve as channels of communication and collaboration, to foster common bibliographic standards, to encourage interchange of personnel—testify to its success.

The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) has become the important international forum for the discussion of library matters. This past January the Executive Board of IFLA, with the help of a Council grant, was in Washington for its first U.S. meeting. Its sessions coincided with those of the American Library Association's midwinter meeting, and this provided IFLA Board members with an important opportunity to meet with many of their American colleagues.

JAPAN-U.S. CONFERENCE: Establishing permanent channels of communication between university and research librarians, and information scientists in the two countries.

A Council grant to the Association of American Library Schools supported a two-day meeting of its board and others to consider the nature of a proposal by the Association to the U. S. Office of Education. The Conference, on "Needs for Research in Library and Information Education," was held in November 1968 under the chairmanship of the Reverend James J. Kortendick, Head of the Catholic University's Department of Library Science and president-elect of the Association. The study, since funded by the Office of Education, has two objectives: to formulate a structured outline of areas of research needed in education for librarianship, including consideration of library science and information science; and, to evaluate and justify some priorities for research among these areas and to identify relevant kinds of research organization.

X. PRESERVATION OF LIBRARY MATERIALS

Catalog Renovation The heavily used main Public Catalog of the Research Libraries of the New York Public Library has been in use for more than seventy years. Much of it is now in a badly worn state. A 1965 dissertation by Seoud Makram Matta, a doctoral candidate in Columbia University's

School of Library Service, indicated that nearly 3 million of the then 8 million (now some 9 million) cards in the catalog were in need of replacement, with many almost unreadable. Rehabilitation costs were estimated at almost \$2 million. In addition to rehabilitation, however, preservation had to be considered. Preservation by photographic reproduction in book form was estimated to cost more than \$1 million, conversion to machine-readable form and computer-produced in book form nearly \$2 million. The New York Public Library, faced with this appalling problem, sought and received a grant from the Council for a review of the Matta study and consideration of various aspects of the problem³³ — one a growing number of libraries will have to face. The inquiry has been completed and a report suggesting alternatives for possible action published.³⁴

The Barrow Research Laboratory The Council again renewed its support of the laboratory established by the late W. J. Barrow in Richmond, Virginia, in 1961 with the Council's aid.³⁵ The Laboratory, now a corporation and under the direction of Dr. R. N. DuPuis, has continued its investigation of the effect of temperature and of humidity on the longevity of book papers in an effort to identify the optimum conditions of storage compatible with use. It has also gone on with its work on the characteristics and behavior of book papers of the 16th-18th centuries, and has returned to research begun but not finished by Mr. Barrow in an attempt to deacidify and strengthen old book papers by a vapor-phase process.

Interest in promoting the use of more stable material is moving beyond the boundaries of libraries and laboratories. Archival agencies, insurance companies, book publishers, and others are showing increasing interest in new papers with permanent/durable qualities. With the backing of the Council, Mr. Barrow developed a formula for manufacturing papers with these qualities. Papers made according to this or similar formulae are now commercially available. One problem, however, is ascertaining, without expensive laboratory testing, whether particular examples of new or older papers are stable. A "do-it-yourself" method is

³³ X: 43.

³⁴ James W. Henderson and Joseph A. Rosenthal, editors. *Library Catalogs: Their Preservation and Maintenance by Photographic and Automated Techniques*. . . . Cambridge, Published for The New York Public Library Astor, Lenox and Tilden Foundations by The M.I.T. Press, [1968]. xi, 267 p. (M.I.T. Report No. 14)

³⁵ VI: 21-22.

described in the sixth of the "Permanence/Durability of the Book" series of reports published by the Laboratory. The report³⁶ describes four color spot tests – for acidity, groundwood, alum, and rosin – which can be made by a layman without the need for elaborate equipment or technical training.

Research at the Imperial College of Science and Technology The disastrous flooding of Florentine libraries in 1966 aroused world-wide concern. The subsequent but less publicized flooding of the Gulbenkian Library in Lisbon was a reminder that these tragedies reoccur. A grant has been made to the Imperial College of Science and Technology, London, for research on fundamental conservation problems, many brought to the fore by the disaster in Florence. The work is being carried out in close association with the Royal College of Art, and is under the joint direction of Peter Waters and J. C. Lewis, both of whom took a prominent part in the early restoration work in Florence.

Among the problems scheduled for investigation are: mud-retention in paper fibers, methods of resizing, effects of fungicides, bleaching, the use of adhesives, and the development of special mending papers. The new techniques will be evaluated in the workshops of the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale in Florence with the cooperation of the Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome. Another important area for work is the improvement of methods of strengthening and mass deacidifying of the paper of post-1840 books, to counter the damaging chemical effects of air pollution and of the manufacturing processes. This will extend and supplement the pioneering work of the Barrow Laboratory.

Research at the University of Chicago Several years ago the Council made a grant to the University of Chicago to enable a young chemist in the Graduate Library School, Richard D. Smith, to pursue an investigation into the deacidification of entire volumes in one operation.³⁷ Since that time two studies resulting from his work, still in progress, have been published; one suggests aspects of preservation and the

³⁶ *Spot Testing for Unstable Modern Book and Record Papers*. Richmond, Virginia, W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., 1969. 28 p.

³⁷ XI: 37.

other discusses acidity and storage conditions in relation to deterioration.³⁸

A National Plan for Preservation of Deteriorating Research Materials

The preceding annual report related the Association of Research Libraries' initiative in seeking a national program for preservation of deteriorating materials, and its sponsorship, with Council assistance, of a pilot project at the Library of Congress to study some procedural problems.³⁹ The final report, by the Library's Brittle Books Project Officer, Norman J. Shaffer, has now been published.⁴⁰ The final paragraph reads: "This pilot study was only the first step in exploring the problems involved in developing a national preservation collection. If physical books are to be saved for future generations, the library community will need more exploratory studies as well as technological breakthroughs. The volume of deteriorating materials requires that action be taken in the near future, if the nineteenth century is not to become known as the beginning of the bookless age."

ALA Committee on Permanent/Durable Paper

An American Library Association Committee on a Permanent/Durable Paper with a membership of both users and producers, was established at the suggestion of the conference on this subject held in Washington, D. C., September 16, 1960.⁴¹ However, the Committee was unable to realize the hopes that had led to its establishment, and it was discontinued this past year.

Part of the Committee's mission has been assumed by the Association's Library Technology Program, which last year negotiated through Committee Z85 (library equipment and supplies) of the United States of America Standards Institute a USA Standard on permanent/durable catalog card stock. Z85 was instituted at the recommendation of the Library Technology Program.

³⁸ Richard D. Smith. "Guidelines for Preservation." *Special Libraries* 59: 346-52. May-June 1968. — "Paper Impermanence as a Consequence of pH and Storage Conditions." *The Library Quarterly* 39: 153-95. April 1969.

³⁹ XII: 28-29.

⁴⁰ Norman J. Shaffer. "Library of Congress Pilot Preservation Project." *College & Research Libraries* 30: 5-11. January 1969.

⁴¹ VI: 23. For a report of the conference, supported by a grant from the Council, see *Permanent/Durable Book Paper, Summary of a Conference Held in Washington, D. C., September 16, 1960*. Sponsored by the American Library Association and the Virginia State Library. Richmond, Virginia, The Virginia State Library, 1960. 53 p.

XI. RESOURCES

A Catalog of Core Books for College Libraries In 1967 John W. Gardner, then Secretary of Health, Education, and Welfare, said⁴² that 50 percent of the four-year colleges and 82 percent of the two-year colleges in the United

States failed to meet ALA standards for minimum size of collections in terms of number of volumes per student.⁴³ With the failure of book budgets to keep pace with rising student enrollments and book prices, little improvement can be anticipated unless some positive steps are taken. There is still another ominous aspect of the situation. According to an unpublished U. S. Office of Education study, the norm for number of librarians in college libraries should be one professional librarian per 375 students. In 1969 the number of budgeted positions was 14,900; the number of filled positions was 13,800 — against a norm of 18,900. This situation is expected to deteriorate and there will be even fewer experienced professional librarians available for the important task of book selection.

The Council has in the past tried to alleviate this situation by supporting the preparation and publication of *Books for College Libraries*, a list of more than 53,000 recommended titles published prior to 1964, and by *Choice*, a book review for academic librarians and others published 11 times a year since 1964.⁴⁴ However, since any institution using these tools must exercise its own selection procedures, these publications have not provided the solution to the basic problem, despite their continuing usefulness.

Core collections of books — pre-selected, acquired, processed, and delivered in packages together with a card or book catalog — could result in very considerable savings to libraries. During the past year and more the Council, with the help of an advisory committee, has thoroughly investigated the subject. The study developed into a detailed program for a “package” which could serve as a basic collection for the libraries of newly established liberal arts colleges and existing ones with inadequate collections.

⁴² John W. Gardner. “A Fancy Gothic Fiction.” *Library Journal* 92: 1896-97. May 15, 1967.

⁴³ [Edwin Castagna, compiler.] *National Inventory of Library Needs*. [Chicago,] American Library Association, 1965.

⁴⁴ *Books for College Libraries* . . . Prepared under the direction of Melvin J. Voigt and Joseph H. Treyz. Chicago, American Library Association Publishing Department, 1967. [x], 1056 p. *Choice*, also published by the Association, is sponsored by the Association of College and Research Libraries. See XI: 19.

(It should be noted that such a collection is intended to include only those titles which academic libraries in general need and to which they would add more titles to meet their particular requirements; the core collection is not expected to represent an adequate collection.)

The American Library Association has volunteered to sponsor the compilation and publication of the basic list of approximately 40,000 titles for the core collection, and the Council has made a grant to the Association for the purpose.

Medieval Manuscripts on Microfilm The Medieval Studies Committee of the University of Pennsylvania Graduate School of Arts and Sciences has been working to establish an archive of microfilmed medieval manuscripts for the use of scholars and for the training of graduate students. As planned, the archive – which will include all the disciplines relating to the life and thought of the period – will be composed of negative microfilms of manuscripts from which enlarged prints can be made, bound in book form, cataloged for ready reference, and available for loan or purchase (subject to prior arrangement with the library owning the original). The archive is expected to ease the burden placed on European repositories by numerous requests for copies from the United States and to make access to basic source materials easier for American scholars. The Council's preceding annual report noted a grant to the University of Pennsylvania for exploratory investigations.⁴⁵ This year the Council made a grant for the Medieval Studies Committee to carry out a pilot project.

Middle Atlantic University Libraries Funds were also allocated this year for a Council-administered project in behalf of a consortium of seven libraries of Upper Middle Atlantic Universities: Delaware, Johns Hopkins, Maryland, Pennsylvania, Pennsylvania State, Princeton, and Rutgers. The project involves preparation of a handbook or guide to all or part of the collections, which may serve as a basis for future cooperative planning.

Statistics on Law Library Resources For many years the American Association of Law Libraries has been in need of statistical information on various aspects of law libraries. As population and litigation have increased, so has the need for more law libraries and more services from them.

⁴⁵ XII: 31-32.

Inevitably, this has prompted numerous questions about their nature and operation for which there are no soundly based answers. The Council has therefore made a grant to the American Association of Law Libraries for its Committee on Statistics to sponsor a statistical survey of law library resources in the United States and Canada. Information will be sought on such matters as: administration and operation, personnel, collections, budgets, physical facilities and services, and users. The information is expected to be useful in establishing standards, planning future improvements, planning new libraries in growing areas, and in other ways. Plans call for computerizing and regular updating of the information.

Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections In 1958, with assistance from the Council, the Library of Congress began compilation of the National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. Since 1964 the Catalog has been carried forward with funds from Congress, with the balance of the Council's final 1963 grant allocated for promoting cooperation in the project.⁴⁶ The sixth volume was published this past year.⁴⁷ It describes 2,244 collections, making a total of 20,661 collections thus far reported. It goes almost without saying that the Catalog has already proved to be an indispensable key to the riches of manuscript source materials in institutions available to researchers in all disciplines.

Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying The Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying, located in the Manuscript Division of the Library of Congress, was established in 1965 with assistance from the Council.⁴⁸ The Center seeks to prevent duplication of effort and the confusion of hit-or-miss microfilming projects by collecting and disseminating information about such projects, past or present. Among other aspects of the Center's work are the assessment of priorities and desiderata, the coordination of efforts, and the collection of information about the availability of materials in foreign repositories for microfilming. Late in 1968 the Council

⁴⁶ XII: 32-33.

⁴⁷ *The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. 1967. Index 1967.* Compiled by the Library of Congress from Reports Provided by American Repositories with Assistance from The Council on Library Resources, Inc. Washington, The Library of Congress, 1968. xxv, 525 p. 28 cms.

⁴⁸ IX: 24; XI; 38-39; XII: 32.

made another grant toward the administrative expenses of the Center for two years. Thereafter, it is hoped, Congressional support can be obtained.

XII. TESTING AND STANDARDIZATION

Library Technology Program The American Library Association's Library Technology Program, which officially marked its 10th anniversary on May 1, 1969, provides a continuing program of testing and standardizing of supplies, equipment, and systems, and of collaborating with industry in the development of improved or new products for libraries. Among its activities this fiscal year have been work on performance standards for library equipment, binding, permanent/durable catalog cards (see p. 35), a library typewriter keyboard, steel shelving, and library chairs. Audiovisual equipment has been another subject of interest.

In addition to answering questions of a technical nature from librarians in various parts of the world, the Library Technology Program continued to report many of its findings in regular columns in the *ALA Bulletin* and *Special Libraries*, and in a bimonthly subscription service, *Library Technology Reports*, now with more than 1,000 subscribers. The report of a three-year study by a Work Simplification Committee appointed by the Danish Library Association was published in book form.⁴⁹ A revised, second edition of *Cleaning and Preserving Bindings and Related Materials*, by Carolyn Horton, widely known expert in the field of conservation of library collections,⁵⁰ has been prepared for publication in the fall of 1969. This is the first in what is intended to be a series constituting a manual on the care of books and other library materials.

The Council has continued its support of the Library Technology Program, founded at the instigation of the Council at a time when the library profession had little guidance available to it in the choice of supplies and equipment. However, as previously indicated,⁵¹ the Council's assistance now represents only 43 percent of LTP's operating budget and a little more than

⁴⁹ Henning Gimbel. Rudolph Ellsworth, translator. *Work Simplification in Danish Public Libraries*. Chicago, Library Technology Program, American Library Association, 1969. xiii, 256 p. (LTP Publication No. 15)

⁵⁰ XII: 31.

⁵¹ XII: 33.

two-thirds of project costs. The balance is met by the American Library Association and self-generated income.

Z39: USA Standards Institute The United States of America Standards Institute has been defined as "a federation of trade, technical, and professional societies, companies, government agencies, labor and consumer interests," and is affiliated with the International Standards Organization. Committee Z39 of the Institute is concerned with standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing activities. Its function is carried on almost entirely by volunteer members of subcommittees, each of which is working toward development of a standard in such fields as machine input records, periodical title abbreviations, bibliographic references, transliteration, and binding. This fiscal year the Council and the National Science Foundation made matching grants to the University of North Carolina in behalf of Z39 to support the Committee's operating expenses, including a small secretariat located in the University Library.⁵² Dr. Jerrold Orne, University Librarian, is chairman of Z39. The Institute will change its name in the fall of 1969 to American National Standards Institute, Inc.

Library Statistics The Council's various grants to promote standardization of library statistics have been recounted in previous annual reports. The preceding one⁵³ listed a grant to the International Federation of Library Associations for a joint meeting of its statistics committee with that of the International Standards Organization and with interested officials of UNESCO. This past fiscal year a progress report was published in a bilingual edition.⁵⁴ The publication contains the report of a 1967 meeting in Paris of committees from IFLA and ISO with

⁵² XI: 41-42.

⁵³ XII: 34-35.

⁵⁴ [K. A. Mallaber, Torben Nielsen, F. W. Torrington, editors.] *The International Standardisation of Library Statistics, A Progress Report. La Normalisation Internationale des Statistiques Relatives au Bibliothèques*. . . . London, International Federation of Library Associations, . . . , International Organization for Standardization, . . . , 1968. 216 p. (IFLA International Manual No. 4)

The foreword to the publication concludes: "Neither the Paris Conference nor the Conference at The Hague would have been possible without the generous financial help provided by the Council on Library Resources, Inc. If, as we believe, more progress has been made in getting international agreement in this field in the last two years than in the previous thirty-five years, no little of the credit must go to the Council for its generous and far-sighted support."

UNESCO officials, and the report of a similar meeting at The Hague the preceding year. It is expected that a final text of an international standard for library statistics will be recommended to the member nations for acceptance at the 1970 UNESCO General Conference.

XIII. CLR FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM

Opportunities for librarians to take time away from their assignments in order to familiarize themselves with the highly complex changes occurring in their profession are much more limited than for other members of the academic community. They, as much as faculty, need the chance to bring themselves up to date, to explore new developments, to widen their horizons. The Council has therefore instituted a Fellowship Program to make these opportunities available,⁵⁵ and in the spring of 1969 announced the first grants under it. Fellowships were awarded to:

Florence Blakely, Head, Reference Department, Duke University
Warren Boes, Director of Libraries, Syracuse University
John M. Dawson, Director of Libraries, University of Delaware
Richard M. Dougherty, Associate Director of Libraries, University of Colorado
Andrew J. Eaton, Director of Libraries, Washington University
James F. Govan, Librarian, Swarthmore College
Tyrus C. Harmsen, Librarian, Occidental College
Miles M. Jackson, Jr., Librarian, Atlanta University
Irving Lieberman, Director, School of Librarianship, University of Washington
Ellsworth Mason, Director of Library Services, Hofstra University
Luella R. Pollock, Librarian, Reed College
Eldred Smith, Head, Loan Department, University of California, Berkeley
Jessie Carney Smith, University Librarian, Fisk University
David Weber, Associate Director of Libraries, Stanford University
Robert Wedgeworth, Assistant Chief Order Librarian, Brown University

A committee headed by Dr. Louis B. Wright, Vice-Chairman of the Council's Board of Directors and Director Emeritus of the Folger Shakespeare Library,⁵⁶ selected the successful candidates

⁵⁵ XII: 35-36.

⁵⁶ Other members are: William S. Dix, Librarian of Princeton University; Robert Vosper, Librarian of the University of California at Los Angeles; and ex officio, Fred C. Cole, President of the Council, and Foster E. Mohrhardt, Senior Program Officer. Mrs. Edith M. Lesser, Secretary of the Council, serves as secretary for the Program.

from among close to 200 nominations received from prominent librarians. The awards, for periods of from three to twelve months, are intended to cover such expenses as travel, per diem, and supplies and equipment incident to a Fellow's project while he is on leave of absence from his institution, which is expected to continue his salary in his absence. The intent of the Fellowship Program precludes an award for work toward an advanced degree.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 14, 1969

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1969, its expenditures and income and sources and applications of cash for the year, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

EXHIBIT I

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
 STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES
 AND FUND BALANCE

ASSETS	June 30	
	1969	1968
Cash (Exhibit III)	\$ 100,856	\$ 118,982
Investments		
United States Treasury Bills, at cost plus discount earned (approximates market)		290,332
Certificates of deposit, at cost plus accrued interest	1,473,022	762,142
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation in quarterly installments of \$500,000 (Note 1)	4,000,000	1,000,000
Prepaid expenses and deposits	6,136	2,278
	<u>\$5,580,014</u>	<u>\$2,173,734</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable	\$1,594,737	\$ 632,685
Fellowships payable	53,051	
Accounts payable, accrued salaries and withheld taxes	6,361	9,144
	<u>1,654,149</u>	<u>641,829</u>
Fund balance at beginning of year	1,531,905	2,420,558
Add—Grant from the Ford Foundation (Note 1)	5,000,000	
	6,531,905	2,420,558
Deduct—Expenditures less income for the year (Exhibit II)	2,606,040	888,653
Fund balance at year end (Note 1)	<u>3,925,865</u>	<u>1,531,905</u>
	<u>\$5,580,014</u>	<u>\$2,173,734</u>

EXHIBIT II

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
 STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME
 (NOTE 2)

EXPENDITURES	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1969	1968
Program expense		
Grants and contracts	\$2,642,179	\$689,609
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded	(431,634)	(42,965)
	<u>2,210,545</u>	<u>646,644</u>
Fellowships	64,950	
Compensation and employee benefits	146,434	
Consultants fees and expenses	17,578	
Travel	14,579	
Other	263	
	<u>2,454,349</u>	<u>646,644</u>
Administrative expense		
Compensation and employee benefits	133,257	196,705
Rent	18,350	13,225
Professional services	36,749	40,784
Travel and meetings	14,239	17,730
Furniture and equipment	4,039	12,733
Printing and duplication	6,411	6,529
Office and other expense	18,294	17,849
	<u>231,339</u>	<u>305,555</u>
	<u>2,685,688</u>	<u>952,199</u>
 INCOME		
Income from investments	<u>79,648</u>	<u>63,546</u>
Expenditures less income	<u>\$2,606,040</u>	<u>\$888,653</u>

EXHIBIT III

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
 STATEMENT OF SOURCE AND APPLICATION
 OF CASH (NOTE 2)

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1969	1968
Cash provided by		
Receipts from Ford Foundation	\$2,000,000	\$ 750,000
Proceeds from disposition of investment securities	5,459,100	2,180,930
Savings account drawings		533,769
Grant refunds	63,239	25,245
	<u>7,522,339</u>	<u>3,489,944</u>
Cash applied to		
Program expense	1,498,602	1,016,775
Administrative expense	242,113	305,745
Purchases of investment securities	5,800,000	2,280,349
Employee travel advances, net	(250)	150
	<u>7,540,465</u>	<u>3,603,019</u>
Cash decrease during the year	(18,126)	(113,075)
Cash, beginning of year	<u>118,982</u>	<u>232,057</u>
Cash, end of year	<u>\$ 100,856</u>	<u>\$ 118,982</u>

N O T E S

- 1) Effective July 1, 1968, The Ford Foundation approved an additional \$5,000,000 grant to the Council, to supplement the \$1,000,000 remaining on the grant approved in 1961, for the continuation and expansion of the Council's program. The grant agreement specifies that the grant will be expended in substantial compliance with an annual budget of \$2,000,000 for a three year period beginning July 1, 1968, and that the grant will be disbursed in quarterly instalments. At June 30, 1968, \$473,936 had been appropriated by the Board of Directors for specific grants and contracts and \$75,600 had been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts of up to \$25,000 or additions to existing grants and contracts of up to \$5,000 each to be made at his discretion.
- 2) With the expansion of the Council's programs certain organizational changes have been made including the addition of employees working directly on specific programs. This concept was apparent at the beginning of the fiscal year and the Council's accounting records were modified so as to reflect the expenses related to these activities as program expenses. Similar expenses incurred during the initial stages of reorganization were classified as administrative expense during the year ended June 30, 1968. It is impracticable to reclassify these expenses for comparative purposes.

EXHIBIT IV

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND
COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1969

	Payable June 30, 1968	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1969
American Association of Law Libraries, Committee on Statistics					
Statistical survey of law library resources in the U. S. and Canada		\$ 20,000		\$ 5,000	\$ 15,000
American Council of Learned Societies					
Study of the problems and needs of research libraries			\$ 5,764	(5,764)	
American Library Association					
Assistance in establishing a quarterly Journal of Information Science & Library Automation	\$ 10,684			6,293	4,391
Assistance to Special Subcommittee on Aid to Italian Libraries			109	(109)	
Evaluation of the work of the Library Technology Program	19,000	2,241		21,241	
First Japan-U.S. Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education *		20,000		19,097	903
Library Technology Program					
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1963			2,640	(2,640)	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1965			13,500	(13,500)	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1966			625	(625)	
Projects of testing and standardization to August 31, 1967	66,851			38,125	28,726
Extension of the Library Technology Program to August 31, 1968	48,100			22,946	25,154
Extension of the Library Technology Program to August 31, 1970		192,400		56,250	136,150
Conservation of Library Materials, Phase II	30,000			7,500	22,500
An evaluation of microform readers for libraries available on the American market		15,760		3,940	11,820
Director's Discretionary Fund, September 1, 1967 - August 31, 1968	5,000		5,377	(377)	
Director's Discretionary Fund, April 1, 1969 - August 31, 1970		15,000		3,000	12,000
Preparation of a manuscript reporting the results of an analytic and comparative study of typography and legibility			810	(810)	
Publication of a book-selection service (Choice) at the college library level	31,850				31,850
A Book Catalog for a core collection for college libraries		290,502			290,502

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1968	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1969
American Library Association (cont'd)					
Support of the work of the ALA Committee on a Permanent/Durable Paper			\$ 7,278	\$(7,278)	
Association of American Library Schools					
Meeting to consider proposal to the Office of Education		\$ 1,500	345	1,155	
Association of Research Libraries					
First (pilot) phase in a National Preservation Program for research materials			2,000	(2,000)	
University Library Management Study		25,000		12,500	\$12,500
Preliminary study for a national foreign newspaper microfilming program		13,000		4,300	8,700
W. J. Barrow Laboratory, Inc.					
Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relative to the preservation of books and other library materials	\$45,212	71,150	19,920	62,206	34,236
Bell & Howell Company					
Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography	9,070		9,070		
Columbia University					
Development of a cataloging code for materials in Pushto, Urdu and Panjabi			253	(253)	
The P. L. 480 Program in American Libraries		3,767		1,884	1,883
Federation of American Societies for Experimental Biology					
Development of criteria for quality control of input in science information systems		20,000		7,500	12,500
The Free Library of Philadelphia					
Development and field-testing of a theft protection system	33,250			33,250	
Georgetown University					
A feasibility study for a joint computer center for five Washington, D. C. university libraries			1,367	(1,367)	
Imperial College of Science and Technology (London)					
Research on the conservation of library materials		75,240		6,270	68,970
Information General Corporation					
A research study for time and cost analysis of library operations		15,000		5,000	10,000
International Business Machines Corporation					
Library Management System (LMS)		300,000	291,500	8,500	
International Federation of Library Associations					
An International Meeting on Cataloging		30,000		16,231	13,769
Support of Mid Winter meeting of the IFLA Executive Board in Washington		2,500	70	2,430	

	Payable June 30, 1968	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1969
Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials, Inc.					
Assistance to National Serials Data Program	\$ 30,000			\$ 15,000	\$ 15,000
Study of the effectiveness of New Serial Titles of libraries in the U.S. and Canada as a continuing record of serial holdings			\$ 139	(139)	
Library of Congress					
Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying (continuation for two years)		\$ 58,377		14,594	43,783
Development of procedures for automated control of thematic map collections	16,769			16,769	
Investigation of feasibility of automating the catalog of the Archive of American Folk Song			1,826	(1,826)	
Pilot Project for the Conversion of Retrospective Cataloging Records to Machine-Readable Form (RECON)		25,000			25,000
A study of the feasibility of converting retrospective cataloging records to a suitable machine-readable form		25,000		25,000	
Support of the work of the Federal Library Committee (supplement)			1,878	(1,878)	
To expedite publication of the MARC Pilot Project Report			545	(545)	
London University, School of Librarianship and Archives					
Preparation of a catalog code for materials in Hindi	3,500			3,500	
Los Angeles County Public Library					
Investigation of the use of optical character recognition equipment in library operations	5,331		5,331		
Massachusetts Institute of Technology					
Project INTREX, October 1, 1968 - June 30, 1970		812,500		317,833	494,667
Michigan State University					
Cost comparison of three methods of converting bibliographical information to machine-readable form			17,688	(17,688)	
Modern Language Association of America					
Preparation for computer-assisted production of MLA International Bibliography			454	(454)	
R. A. Morgan Company					
Construction and testing of a prototype of a bibliographer's camera	14,886	809		11,209	4,486
Mt. San Antonio College Foundation					
Development of a teaching machine for instruction in use of library tools (revised project)	5,000				5,000
National Archives and Records Service					
Computer indexing and composition of archival/manuscript finding aids	21,000			21,000	

	Payable June 30, 1968	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1969
National Book Committee, Inc. Toward solutions of the library manpower shortage problem			\$ 653	\$ (653)	
National Endowment for the Humanities College Library Program		\$250,000		250,000	
Support of the Wellesley Index to Victorian Periodicals		2,349		2,349	
New England Board of Higher Education Continuation of NELINET (New England Library Information Network) project. Establishment of a computer-based regional library processing center		151,028		66,000	\$ 85,028
Planning a computer-based regional technical processing center, completion of work commenced under CLR-385	\$123,271		20	123,251	
North Carolina State Board of Higher Education Feasibility study of a state research depository library		10,000		6,500	3,500
Mrs. F. A. Ogunsheye To assist Mrs. Ogunsheye to remain in the U.S. on a study tour until November 2, 1968		200		200	
Purdue Research Foundation Characteristics of library collections which affect their support of graduate educational programs — design of a study			410	(410)	
San Antonio Public Library Books-by-mail public library circulation system	17,500			5,000	12,500
School of Librarianship & Archives, University College (London) Union Catalog of Urdu Mss in the United Kingdom		12,000		6,000	6,000
Support for Guy R. Lyle's study of library duplication of special collections and of the need for a code of practice for reprint publishers; and other library programs*	1,500			1,004	496
System Development Corporation Library Information System Time-Sharing System (LISTS)		79,931		19,980	59,951
U.S. Army, Office, Chief of Engineers Study of the characteristics and relationships between technical libraries and other information facilities		20,000		20,000	
U.S. National Bureau of Standards Study and experimentation in computer composition of library materials			438	(438)	
University of California Preparation and publication of a handbook on data processing for libraries	34,249				34,249

*Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1968	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1969
University of California, Berkeley					
Support for publication of the final report on CLR-361, experiment in library application of facsimile transmission equipment, Phase 2			\$ 622	\$ (622)	
University of California, Santa Cruz					
Development of a machine-manipulable classification scheme for slides in the sciences	\$ 14,131	\$ 9,950	1,618	22,463	
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600		24,600		
University of North Carolina (on behalf of American Standards Association Sectional Committee Z39)					
Development of standards in library work and documentation	12,300	61,275	7,639	14,874	\$ 51,062
University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia					
Planning a central repository of microfilms of European Medieval manuscripts			1,859	(1,859)	
Proposal for a Middle Atlantic States - University of Pennsylvania Archive of Medieval Manuscripts on film — Stage II		8,500			8,500
Various *					
Expenses connected with the "Laboratory" Guide to resources of a consortium of seven Middle Atlantic University Libraries	6,203		4,986	1,217	
Travel grants to attend meetings abroad	3,428	2,200	300	1,367	2,200
Fellowship Program *		64,950		11,899	53,051
TOTAL	\$632,685	\$2,707,129	\$431,634	\$1,260,392	\$1,647,788

*Council-administered project

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The picture of the scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the front cover, is adapted from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine*, Paris, 1588. The original engraving has been reproduced in the Council's Third and subsequent annual reports.

The photographs of the library at the Goddard Space Flight Center, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, which appears on the inside cover, are reproduced by courtesy of the Center, Greenbelt, Maryland.

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*To me every hour of the light and dark is a miracle,
Every cubic inch of space is a miracle.*

— Whitman, "Miracles" (*Leaves of Grass*).

